

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INCOME LEVEL AND ATTITUDE TOWARD TAX EVASION: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Several studies have examined the relationship between attitude toward tax evasion and the level of income. However, those studies were limited to a single country. The results have been mixed. In some cases, tax evasion was found to be more acceptable among the lower income group. In other studies, the exact opposite was found. A third group of studies found no significant relationship between income level and the acceptability of tax evasion. The present study uses data from the most recent World Values Survey, which interviewed more than 125,000 people in nearly 80 countries. The survey included a question on attitude toward tax evasion. This study examines this data with the goal of determining if there is a relationship between income level and attitude toward tax evasion.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous studies have been done on various aspects of tax evasion over the years. Most studies that appear in the public finance literature, if they address the question of tax evasion at all, take a utilitarian perspective and address questions of what causes it (Khlif & Ashek, 2015) or how to reduce it (Buchanan, 1967; Buchanan & Flowers, 1975; Musgrave, 1959, 1986; Richardson, 2006).

Fewer studies examine ethical aspects of taxation (Bird-Pollan, 2020; Blum & Kalven, 1953; Frecknall-Hughes, 2020; McGee, 1994, 2004, 2006; van Brederode, 2020), or whether certain taxes are fair (Blum & Kalven, 1953; Green, 2020; Jouvenel, 1952; McGee, 1999). Robert Nozick, the eminent Harvard philosopher, has likened the income tax to a form of slavery, since it confiscates a portion of the fruits of one's labor (Nozick, 1974).

A few scholars question the very justification for taxation (Block, 1989, 1993; Block & Torsell, 2020; Chodorov, 1962). Others have found tax evasion to be more acceptable in some cases than in others (Crowe, 1944; McGee, 2006, 2012).

A few people have questioned whether the penalties for tax evasion might be too severe, since surveys have found that a major segment of the population believe that tax evasion is not nearly as serious an offense as government officials would have us believe (Burton, Karlinsky & Blanthorne, 2005; Karlinsky, Burton & Blanthorne, 2004; McGee, Petrides & Ross, 2012; McGee, Gelman & Tarangelo, 2014).

Culture has been found to play a role in attitudes toward tax evasion (Richardson, Tsakumis, Curatola & Porcano, 2007). That could partially explain why the residents of different countries view tax evasion differently, even in cases where they share a common religion (McGee, 2012).

Numerous surveys have been conducted to learn peoples' views on the ethics of tax evasion (Alm, Martinez-Vazquez & Torgler, 2005; Collymore, 2020a & b; McGee & Smith, 2012; Torgler & Valev, 2012; Torgler, 2010, 2012). McGee (2012) summarized more than 100 such studies. The one thing these studies have in common is that a large segment of practically every population can justify some level of tax evasion.

Some studies have examined the relationship between income level and attitude toward the acceptability of tax evasion. The most comprehensive study (McGee, 2012a) summarized many of those studies. The results of those studies were mixed. In one group of studies, there was a positive correlation between income level and the acceptability of tax evasion. In a second group of studies, the correlation was negative. In a third group of studies, the relationship was either curvilinear or unclear. Although the McGee (2012a) study found conflicting correlations, he did not identify whether there was a dominant correlation. The present study aims to fill this gap in the literature, using new data that were not available when McGee (2012a) conducted his study.

METHODOLOGY

Every five years or so, starting in 1981, the people who publish the World Values Surveys (Haerpfer, 2020) conduct individual face-to-face interviews with a wide range of individuals from different educational, social, and religious backgrounds. The latest, Wave 7, asked hundreds of questions to more than 125,000 individuals in nearly 80 countries. One of those questions asked about the justifiability of tax evasion. The interviewer asked respondents to choose a number from 1 to 10 to indicate whether tax evasion was never justified (1) to always justified (10). Not every question was asked in every country. The tax evasion question was asked in 76 countries.

In this study, we examined the relationship between income level and attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion. The database divided income level into three groups – lower, middle and higher – without going into much detail about where the cut-off might be separating any of the categories. We determined whether the differences between levels of income were significant using a two-tailed student t-test that compared the mean, standard deviation and sample size of the two groups that had the lowest and highest mean scores. The results are presented below.

FINDINGS

An examination of the results found that there are several different correlations between income level and attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion. Some were more dominant than others.

Table 1 lists all 77 of the countries included in the database and shows the means, standard deviations and sample sizes for each of the three income levels. P values were also calculated.

Table 1
Relationship between Acceptability of Tax Evasion and Level of Income
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P values
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Albania	1.59	1.64	804	1.68	1.86	497	1.62	1.67	154	0.8358
Andorra	1.63	1.59	131	1.68	1.56	660	2.05	1.81	92	0.0681
Argentina	2.04	1.80	170	2.18	1.97	730	1.82	1.80	57	0.1817
Armenia	3.46	2.79	633	3.88	3.15	551	4.89	3.39	252	0.0001
Australia	1.93	2.02	407	2.02	1.79	1,169	2.29	1.96	168	0.0505
Austria	1.80	1.60	507	1.88	1.69	402	1.95	1.77	499	0.1587
Azerbaijan	2.77	2.47	620	3.33	3.00	583	3.16	2.72	424	0.0004
Bangladesh	1.78	1.18	206	1.75	1.15	786	1.45	0.91	208	0.0015
Belarus	2.99	2.46	273	3.34	2.48	554	3.39	2.39	535	0.0262
Bolivia	1.94	1.87	445	2.06	1.97	1,332	2.19	2.18	236	0.1179
Bosnia & Herzegovina	1.74	2.08	679	1.67	1.88	570	1.89	1.99	429	0.0745
Brazil	3.05	3.14	660	3.03	2.89	887	3.00	2.81	94	0.8838
Bulgaria	1.58	1.71	661	1.71	1.71	382	1.73	1.63	404	0.1577
Chile	2.77	2.51	302	2.51	2.16	627	3.04	2.41	47	0.1081
China	1.43	1.23	1,117	1.54	1.32	1,812	1.86	1.83	80	0.0037
Colombia	2.07	2.34	577	2.10	2.16	767	1.80	1.95	176	0.0911
Croatia	1.76	2.11	495	1.98	2.12	424	2.21	2.38	413	0.0026
Cyprus	1.40	1.28	179	1.53	1.48	718	2.00	2.16	66	0.0083
Czech Republic	2.07	2.02	443	1.99	1.96	412	2.30	2.06	557	0.0183
Denmark	1.62	1.36	999	1.56	1.34	970	1.57	1.33	1,233	0.3243
Ecuador	2.49	2.62	330	2.24	2.23	717	2.50	2.55	143	0.9694
Egypt	1.61	1.32	171	1.49	1.32	926	1.47	1.33	17	0.2595
Estonia	1.70	1.60	344	2.14	2.03	342	2.48	2.20	471	0.0001
Ethiopia	1.74	2.36	397	1.42	1.76	736	1.68	2.29	95	0.0100
Finland	1.77	1.59	369	1.77	1.51	396	1.90	1.59	370	0.2668
France	2.05	1.93	586	2.13	2.02	516	1.88	1.63	630	0.0206
Georgia	2.55	2.32	604	2.17	2.01	711	2.08	2.11	723	0.0001
Germany – East & West	1.54	1.37	982	1.58	1.39	1,769	1.63	1.41	664	0.1965
Greece	1.81	1.68	355	1.64	1.38	755	1.72	1.48	40	0.0750
Guatemala	2.75	2.97	119	2.29	2.12	785	2.44	2.54	274	0.0379
Hong Kong	1.82	1.59	616	2.23	1.85	1,380	3.41	2.8	69	0.0001
Hungary	1.38	1.14	450	1.50	1.44	441	1.67	1.46	318	0.1110
Iceland	1.81	1.63	409	1.83	1.44	579	1.84	1.54	508	0.7752
Indonesia	2.97	3.02	1,219	2.27	2.16	1,658	2.74	2.87	315	0.0001
Iran	2.26	2.27	621	2.33	2.39	763	2.85	2.86	95	0.0233
Iraq	2.66	2.11	358	2.82	2.23	747	2.37	2.10	95	0.0626
Italy	2.28	2.03	710	2.05	1.87	586	1.75	1.62	349	0.0001
Japan	1.31	1.14	582	1.19	0.73	437	1.23	0.91	186	0.0546
Jordan	1.96	2.10	475	2.17	2.34	675	2.51	2.81	45	0.1047
Kazakhstan	2.31	2.25	121	3.05	2.53	983	2.99	2.63	125	0.0022
Kyrgyzstan	2.33	2.57	218	2.22	2.41	828	2.30	2.58	133	0.9157
Lebanon	2.24	1.90	193	2.53	1.96	837	3.08	2.56	170	0.0004
Lithuania	2.55	2.10	484	2.61	2.07	380	2.90	2.28	388	0.0655

Macau	2.43	2.04	152	2.25	1.75	828	2.66	1.66	38	0.1574
Malaysia	3.64	2.63	426	3.33	2.48	751	3.14	2.34	136	0.0481
Mexico	2.87	2.58	709	3.04	2.52	823	3.22	2.85	185	0.1084
Montenegro	2.05	1.81	343	1.88	1.76	255	1.95	2.01	231	0.2509
Myanmar	1.60	1.34	322	1.60	1.39	773	1.88	1.64	105	0.0799
Netherlands	2.27	1.99	746	2.07	1.69	654	2.00	1.70	575	0.0094
New Zealand	1.72	1.72	268	1.85	1.69	370	1.80	1.34	313	0.6725
Nicaragua	2.16	2.47	388	2.06	2.22	669	2.90	3.16	143	0.4986
Nigeria	1.68	1.55	432	1.89	1.69	714	1.57	1.66	82	0.1042
North Macedonia	1.81	1.90	357	1.59	1.46	296	1.58	1.69	208	0.1492
Norway	1.81	1.76	404	1.72	1.58	382	1.43	0.97	286	0.0010
Pakistan	1.58	1.62	645	2.00	1.97	1,070	3.05	3.34	167	0.0001
Peru	1.99	2.01	313	1.78	1.61	953	2.05	2.08	121	0.0940
Philippines	3.86	3.16	418	4.03	2.95	703	5.15	3.33	79	0.0010
Poland	1.44	1.17	392	1.6	1.57	350	1.56	1.37	351	0.7194
Puerto Rico	1.50	1.77	234	1.42	1.39	719	1.87	2.15	153	0.0658
Romania	2.60	2.81	842	2.33	2.46	1,260	2.34	2.44	329	0.1405
Russian Federation	3.52	2.77	1,084	3.76	2.84	1,581	4.00	2.90	635	0.0007
Serbia	2.06	2.27	719	3.00	3.15	1,023	2.31	2.51	456	0.0001
Slovakia	2.78	2.10	279	2.45	2.08	366	2.81	2.14	331	0.0247
Slovenia	1.70	1.50	265	1.78	1.59	394	1.74	1.64	288	0.5173
South Korea	1.91	1.16	196	2.29	1.58	1,028	1.90	1.55	21	0.2629
Spain	3.04	3.01	391	2.52	2.40	267	2.33	2.11	236	0.0015
Sweden	1.87	1.62	268	1.69	1.41	411	1.61	1.20	464	0.0135
Switzerland	2.24	2.20	946	1.88	1.73	1,043	1.92	1.59	894	0.0001
Taiwan ROC	1.74	1.49	359	1.72	1.38	827	1.95	1.90	37	0.3304
Tajikistan	2.49	1.47	85	2.44	1.54	986	2.25	1.98	129	0.3397
Thailand	1.78	1.38	369	1.76	1.49	1,021	1.43	1.09	110	0.0150
Tunisia	2.32	2.15	356	1.76	1.61	735	1.72	1.61	106	0.0081
Turkey	1.45	1.27	347	1.68	1.57	1,738	2.10	2.32	244	0.0001
United Kingdom	1.69	1.54	533	1.77	1.72	523	1.62	1.40	471	0.1345
United States	2.11	2.07	526	1.99	1.74	1,793	2.60	2.50	212	0.1838
Vietnam	2.41	1.96	165	2.90	2.06	972	2.89	2.17	63	0.0045
Zimbabwe	1.88	2.34	618	1.85	2.10	545	1.70	1.78	50	0.5953

Table 2 lists the 32 countries where the income level demographic is not significant at the 10 percent level.

Table 2
Countries Where Income Level is Not Significant (10%)
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P values
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Albania	1.59	1.64	804	1.68	1.86	497	1.62	1.67	154	0.8358
Argentina	2.04	1.80	170	2.18	1.97	730	1.82	1.80	57	0.1817
Austria	1.80	1.60	507	1.88	1.69	402	1.95	1.77	499	0.1587
Bolivia	1.94	1.87	445	2.06	1.97	1,332	2.19	2.18	236	0.1179
Brazil	3.05	3.14	660	3.03	2.89	887	3.00	2.81	94	0.8838
Bulgaria	1.58	1.71	661	1.71	1.71	382	1.73	1.63	404	0.1577
Chile	2.77	2.51	302	2.51	2.16	627	3.04	2.41	47	0.1081
Denmark	1.62	1.36	999	1.56	1.34	970	1.57	1.33	1,233	0.3243
Ecuador	2.49	2.62	330	2.24	2.23	717	2.50	2.55	143	0.9694
Egypt	1.61	1.32	171	1.49	1.32	926	1.47	1.33	17	0.2595
Finland	1.77	1.59	369	1.77	1.51	396	1.90	1.59	370	0.2668
Germany – East & West	1.54	1.37	982	1.58	1.39	1,769	1.63	1.41	664	0.1965
Hungary	1.38	1.14	450	1.50	1.44	441	1.67	1.46	318	0.1110
Iceland	1.81	1.63	409	1.83	1.44	579	1.84	1.54	508	0.7752
Jordan	1.96	2.10	475	2.17	2.34	675	2.51	2.81	45	0.1047
Kyrgyzstan	2.33	2.57	218	2.22	2.41	828	2.30	2.58	133	0.9157
Macau	2.43	2.04	152	2.25	1.75	828	2.66	1.66	38	0.1574
Mexico	2.87	2.58	709	3.04	2.52	823	3.22	2.85	185	0.1084
Montenegro	2.05	1.81	343	1.88	1.76	255	1.95	2.01	231	0.2509
New Zealand	1.72	1.72	268	1.85	1.69	370	1.80	1.34	313	0.6725
Nicaragua	2.16	2.47	388	2.06	2.22	669	2.90	3.16	143	0.4986
Nigeria	1.68	1.55	432	1.89	1.69	714	1.57	1.66	82	0.1042
North Macedonia	1.81	1.90	357	1.59	1.46	296	1.58	1.69	208	0.1492
Poland	1.44	1.17	392	1.6	1.57	350	1.56	1.37	351	0.7194
Romania	2.60	2.81	842	2.33	2.46	1,260	2.34	2.44	329	0.1405
Slovenia	1.70	1.50	265	1.78	1.59	394	1.74	1.64	288	0.5173
South Korea	1.91	1.16	196	2.29	1.58	1,028	1.90	1.55	21	0.2629
Taiwan ROC	1.74	1.49	359	1.72	1.38	827	1.95	1.90	37	0.3304
Tajikistan	2.49	1.47	85	2.44	1.54	986	2.25	1.98	129	0.3397
United Kingdom	1.69	1.54	533	1.77	1.72	523	1.62	1.40	471	0.1345
United States	2.11	2.07	526	1.99	1.74	1,793	2.60	2.50	212	0.1838
Zimbabwe	1.88	2.34	618	1.85	2.10	545	1.70	1.78	50	0.5953

Table 3 lists the 19 countries where acceptability of tax evasion increases significantly (10%) as the income level increases.

Table 3
Countries Where Acceptability Increases as Income Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P values
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Andorra	1.63	1.59	131	1.68	1.56	660	2.05	1.81	92	0.0681
Armenia	3.46	2.79	633	3.88	3.15	551	4.89	3.39	252	0.0001
Australia	1.93	2.02	407	2.02	1.79	1,169	2.29	1.96	168	0.0505
Belarus	2.99	2.46	273	3.34	2.48	554	3.39	2.39	535	0.0262
China	1.43	1.23	1,117	1.54	1.32	1,812	1.86	1.83	80	0.0037
Croatia	1.76	2.11	495	1.98	2.12	424	2.21	2.38	413	0.0026
Cyprus	1.40	1.28	179	1.53	1.48	718	2.00	2.16	66	0.0083
Estonia	1.70	1.60	344	2.14	2.03	342	2.48	2.20	471	0.0001
Hong Kong	1.82	1.59	616	2.23	1.85	1,380	3.41	2.8	69	0.0001
Iran	2.26	2.27	621	2.33	2.39	763	2.85	2.86	95	0.0233
Kazakhstan	2.31	2.25	121	3.05	2.53	983	2.99	2.63	125	0.0022
Lebanon	2.24	1.90	193	2.53	1.96	837	3.08	2.56	170	0.0004
Lithuania	2.55	2.10	484	2.61	2.07	380	2.90	2.28	388	0.0655
Myanmar	1.60	1.34	322	1.60	1.39	773	1.88	1.64	105	0.0799
Pakistan	1.58	1.62	645	2.00	1.97	1,070	3.05	3.34	167	0.0001
Philippines	3.86	3.16	418	4.03	2.95	703	5.15	3.33	79	0.0010
Russian Federation	3.52	2.77	1,084	3.76	2.84	1,581	4.00	2.90	635	0.0007
Turkey	1.45	1.27	347	1.68	1.57	1,738	2.10	2.32	244	0.0001
Vietnam	2.41	1.96	165	2.90	2.06	972	2.89	2.17	63	0.0045

Table 4 lists the 12 countries where acceptability of tax evasion decreases significantly (10%) as the income level increases.

Table 4
Countries Where Acceptability Decreases as Income Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P values
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Bangladesh	1.78	1.18	206	1.75	1.15	786	1.45	0.91	208	0.0015
Colombia	2.07	2.34	577	2.10	2.16	767	1.80	1.95	176	0.0911
Georgia	2.55	2.32	604	2.17	2.01	711	2.08	2.11	723	0.0001
Italy	2.28	2.03	710	2.05	1.87	586	1.75	1.62	349	0.0001
Malaysia	3.64	2.63	426	3.33	2.48	751	3.14	2.34	136	0.0481
Netherlands	2.27	1.99	746	2.07	1.69	654	2.00	1.70	575	0.0094
Norway	1.81	1.76	404	1.72	1.58	382	1.43	0.97	286	0.0010
Spain	3.04	3.01	391	2.52	2.40	267	2.33	2.11	236	0.0015
Sweden	1.87	1.62	268	1.69	1.41	411	1.61	1.20	464	0.0135
Switzerland	2.24	2.20	946	1.88	1.73	1,043	1.92	1.59	894	0.0001
Thailand	1.78	1.38	369	1.76	1.49	1,021	1.43	1.09	110	0.0150
Tunisia	2.32	2.15	356	1.76	1.61	735	1.72	1.61	106	0.0081

Table 5 lists the 4 countries where acceptability of tax evasion increases, then decreases significantly (10%) as the income level increases.

Table 5
Countries Where Acceptability Increases, then Decreases as Income Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P values
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Azerbaijan	2.77	2.47	620	3.33	3.00	583	3.16	2.72	424	0.0004
France	2.05	1.93	586	2.13	2.02	516	1.88	1.63	630	0.0206
Iraq	2.66	2.11	358	2.82	2.23	747	2.37	2.10	95	0.0626
Serbia	2.06	2.27	719	3.00	3.15	1,023	2.31	2.51	456	0.0001

Table 6 lists the 10 countries where acceptability of tax evasion decreases, then increases significantly (10%) as the income level increases.

Table 6
Countries Where Acceptability Decreases, then Increases as Income Level Increases
(1 = never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

	Lower			Middle			Higher			P values
	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	Mean	S.D.	n	
Bosnia & Herzegovina	1.74	2.08	679	1.67	1.88	570	1.89	1.99	429	0.0745
Czech Republic	2.07	2.02	443	1.99	1.96	412	2.30	2.06	557	0.0183
Ethiopia	1.74	2.36	397	1.42	1.76	736	1.68	2.29	95	0.0100
Greece	1.81	1.68	355	1.64	1.38	755	1.72	1.48	40	0.0750
Guatemala	2.75	2.97	119	2.29	2.12	785	2.44	2.54	274	0.0379
Indonesia	2.97	3.02	1,219	2.27	2.16	1,658	2.74	2.87	315	0.0001
Japan	1.31	1.14	582	1.19	0.73	437	1.23	0.91	186	0.0546
Peru	1.99	2.01	313	1.78	1.61	953	2.05	2.08	121	0.0940
Puerto Rico	1.50	1.77	234	1.42	1.39	719	1.87	2.15	153	0.0658
Slovakia	2.78	2.10	279	2.45	2.08	366	2.81	2.14	331	0.0247

Table 7 presents a summary of the findings. If one defines significance at 10 percent, then income is not a significant demographic variable 41.5 percent of the time. If significance is defined at 5 percent, that percentage rises to 55.8 percent.

In the cases where income is a significant demographic variable, there seems to be four different relationships, the most frequent one being in cases where the acceptability of tax evasion increases as income level increases.

**Table 7
Summary**

	At 10% Confidence Level		At 5% Confidence Level	
	#	%	#	%
Income level is not a significant demographic variable	32	41.5	43	55.8
Acceptability of tax evasion increases as income level increases	19	24.7	15	19.5
Acceptability of tax evasion decreases as income level increases	12	15.6	11	14.3
Acceptability of tax evasion increases, then decreases as income level increases	4	5.2	3	3.9
Acceptability of tax evasion decreases, then increases as income level increases	10	13.0	5	6.5
Totals	77	100.0	77	100.0

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main conclusion is that there are several different correlations between view toward the justifiability of tax evasion and income level, which was expected. Our findings confirm the findings of other studies. However, the present study is more comprehensive than other studies because we examined many more countries, and we determined which correlation was dominant, something no other study has done.

There are several other avenues for future research. Perhaps the most obvious one is to determine why there is more than one correlation. In some countries, the correlation is positive while in other it is negative. The correlation for a third group of countries is curvilinear, but we found more than one curvilinear relationship. One might speculate as to the reasons for the differences. Culture undoubtedly plays a role. Gender, age, level of education, ethnicity, religion, and social class probably play a role as well. The World Values Survey data did not ask participants for the reasons behind their answers. Some future study could do that, but it would have to be on a smaller scale than that of the World Values Survey because of cost and human resources considerations.

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